

State Policy on Youth in New Uzbekistan

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Abstract:

This article deals with the organizational and legal issues of state youth policy at a new stage of development in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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Introduction. In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been doing a lot to educate young people in the spirit of respect for national and human values, to raise a spiritually mature and physically healthy generation, to protect their rights and interests. In particular, the state has created a system of socio-economic, organizational and legal measures to create conditions for the social formation of young people and the development of their intellectual, creative and other potential, its result can be seen in the achievements and victories of young people.

While speaking about the state youth policy in the New Uzbekistan, it should be noted that from the first days of Sh.M.Mirziyoyev as the President of Uzbekistan, important components of the state youth policy have been revised. The work in this area is defined in the new edition by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy" No. ZRU-406, adopted on September 14, 2016.

In the country's public policy, the issue of the youth, who make up 64.0% of the population, has been on the agenda. That is why, today these processes have a special place in the policy of the President, which is based on justice and humanity, directly pursued by the President.

As the head of state said, "It is time to take our work to a new level, to create modern job places for our youth and to ensure that they take their rightful place in life. All the forces and opportunities of our state and society will be mobilized for the development of our younger generation, who will be independent-minded, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, will be happy and equal to their peers in any field in the world."

Material and Methods. In the implementation of the state youth policy in the New Uzbekistan, systematic work is being carried out in our country aimed at the harmonious upbringing of the younger generation, the creation of all necessary conditions for them to take an independent step in life.

On June 30, 2020, with the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Agency for Youth Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established to implement a unified state policy in the field and areas related to youth. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved a program of additional measures for the further development of state youth policy in Uzbekistan. In particular, the program provides the creation of a youth portal of Uzbekistan, which will include the formation of national indices for the evaluation of youth policy, as well as a database of youth legislation. The activities envisaged in the program are funded by the agency directly or through the distribution of government grants and subsidies to non-governmental organizations in the form of social orders.

The Committee on Youth, Culture and Sports of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Commission on Youth Affairs of the Legislative Chamber were established. At the same time, in order to ensure the implementation of the State Program "Year of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy", the Senate Council on the establishment of the Youth Parliament under the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established.

In the elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan in December 2019, 9 (6%) young people were elected deputies, while 10% of deputies in local councils are young people.

The state program "Year of Youth Support and Public Health" identifies urgent tasks for the introduction of a new system of work with youth, emphasizing the need for the President to organize work with youth in two important areas. The first is to support youth entrepreneurship and provide them with employment through vocational training, and the second is to organize meaningful leisure time for young people. In this regard, projects such as "100 ideas for Uzbekistan", "Youth: 1 + 1", "Every entrepreneur is a supporter of youth", family business development programs and "Project Factory", "Youth Small Industrial Zones" are being implemented.

Particular attention is paid to equipping the "Welcome to Work" mono-centers and professional colleges, developing professional standards and improving the skills of teachers. The Youth: 1 + 1 program connects boys and girls to entrepreneurs, develops their business skills, provides them with privileged loans and helps them start their own businesses.

According to the No. PF-6208 decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2021 "On additional measures to support entrepreneurship and employment of youth, their social protection and meaningful organization of leisure time" from May 1, 2021 to January 1, 2023 on the involvement of young people in entrepreneurship, providing them with permanent employment to employers (budget organizations, state enterprises (except for legal entities with a state share of 50% or more in the capital) the amount of social tax paid by them for employees not older than 25 years will be fully refunded from the State budget; to the young people listed in the "Youth Book", for the purchase of equipment and tools in order to start their entrepreneurship and self-employment it will be given subsidies from the account of "Youth Book" in the amount of not more than 40 times the amount of the basic calculation; Entrepreneurs who employ unemployed young people included in the Youth Book will be provided with benefits from rent payments when renting state property.

Results. In order to pay more attention to young people, to involve them in culture, arts, physical culture and sports, to develop their skills in using information technology, to promote reading among young people, and to increase women's employment, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan put forward 5 important initiatives. In short, 5 important initiatives have been met with great interest by our people, especially our youth.

3843 people were employed through the state program "Our Youth Future", 13232 people under the state program "Every family is an entrepreneur", 14605 people in horticulture, 70072 people in public works, 17786 people through job fairs and other areas (Employment Assistance Centers) 85,472 young people were employed. As part of the state program, a total of 1 trillion 756.5 billion soums were allocated for 8,380 business projects and 41,777 new jobs were created.

More than 3,300 young families in the country have been provided with "Youth Homes" and more than 150 billion soums of initial payments have been made.

25 coworking centers "Young Entrepreneurs" in the regions and 157 "Youth Labor Guzar" complexes were put into operation, which created a total of 1,787 new jobs.

Discussion. In his speech at the joint session of the Oliy Majlis dedicated to the inauguration, the newly elected President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: We will resolutely pursue the path of democratic reforms based on the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan.

In it, the head of our state said, "We will continue to focus on educating our young people, especially girls, to be healthy and mature, to realize their abilities and talents, to develop the spirit of love and devotion to the Motherland, national and universal values. "It's a big deal," he said. This means that in the next five years of development of our country, youth issues will again become a priority.

Conclusion. In conclusion, studying the work done on youth policy in our country, we can see that measures are being taken in our country to form a harmoniously developed generation, to educate young people spiritually, morally and physically healthy, to make them active participants in ongoing reforms. The adoption of a new version of the Law on State Youth Policy will play an important role in bringing the work in this area to a new level.

REFERENCES:

- Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Together we will build a free and prosperous, democratic state of Uzbekistan. T.: Uzbekistan. 2016.
- Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. T.: Uzbekistan. 2017.
- Speech of the newly elected President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the joint session of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis dedicated to the inauguration ceremony. 06.11.21 // www.president.uz/oz/lists/view/4743
- Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy". September 14, 2016, No. ORQ-406.
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 30, 2020 Decree No. PF-6017 "On measures to radically reform the state youth policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan and bring it to a new level."
- Resolution of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 167-IV of March 11, 2020.
- Results of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development in Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 "Factbook". - T., 2021.
- Collection of handouts of the training seminar for the representatives of the Agency for Youth Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the community - T., 2021.

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